

Conference Abstract

Developing a Robust SDM Pipeline for Predicting Climate-Driven Shifts in Freshwater Fish Distributions

Mi-Jung Bae[‡], Seo-Ha Kim[‡], Dae-Seong Lee[§], Da-Young Lee[§], Young-Seuk Park[§]

[‡] Nakdonggang National Institute of Biological Resources, Sangju-si, Republic of Korea
[§] KyungHee University, Seoul, Republic of Korea

Corresponding author: Mi-Jung Bae (mjbae@nnibr.re.kr)

Received: 14 Feb 2025 | Published: 28 May 2025

Citation: Bae M-J, Kim S-H, Lee D-S, Lee D-Y, Park Y-S (2025) Developing a Robust SDM Pipeline for Predicting Climate-Driven Shifts in Freshwater Fish Distributions. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e150278. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e150278>

Abstract

Understanding climate-induced shifts in freshwater biodiversity requires rigorous modeling approaches. This study applies a spatially explicit species distribution modeling (SDM) framework, incorporating high-resolution (1 km) environmental predictors and 3,307 field survey sites collected between 2016 and 2022 in South Korea. Using Maxent modeling, we assessed the potential distribution shifts of 130 freshwater fish species under three climate scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5). To enhance model accuracy and applicability across regions, we implemented a robust preprocessing pipeline, including spatial filtering to correct sampling bias, multicollinearity reduction (Pearson correlation and variance inflation factor), pseudo-absence generation, and ensemble modeling to minimize uncertainty. Model performance was validated using AUC and TSS metrics, ensuring reliable predictions for conservation planning. Our results indicate that 48 species are at risk of significant range loss by 2080, with climate-driven contractions disproportionately affecting endemic and endangered species, in addition to cold-water taxa. Specifically, 17 endemic species and 6 nationally endangered species, including *Coreoleuciscus splendidus* and *Cottus koreanus*, were identified as highly vulnerable, highlighting the urgent need for conservation interventions. Regional projections pinpointed biodiversity loss hotspots, particularly in the Yeongsan and Nakdong River basins. This study demonstrates how a

reproducible SDM pipeline, combining rigorous preprocessing and climate scenario analysis, can provide actionable insights for freshwater conservation planning. Our approach is adaptable to other regions, offering a transferable framework for assessing climate-driven biodiversity shifts in freshwater ecosystems.

Keywords

species distribution model, freshwater biodiversity, climate change, Shared Socioeconomic Pathways

Presenting author

Mi-Jung Bae

Presented at

ORAL

Funding program

This work was supported by a grant from the Nakdonggang National Institute of Biological Resources (NNIBR), funded by the Ministry of Environment (MOE) of the Republic of Korea (NNIBR20252105).

Grant title

Assessing the Impacts of Climate Change on the Distribution and Habitat Suitability of Freshwater Species

Ethics and security

This study was conducted in accordance with national and institutional ethical guidelines for biodiversity research.

Author contributions

Mi-Jung Bae: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing-original draft, Writing-review and editing

Seo-Ha Kim: Data curation

Dae-Seong Lee: Data curation, Methodology, Visualization

Da-Young Lee: Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology

Young-Seuk Park: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.